

Impact analysis of the time elapsed between mixing and placing on compressive strength of concrete for commercial production

Laxmi Prasad Sapkota, Master's Scholar, Construction Management, Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Urlabari – 3, Morang, Nepal.

A.K. Mishra*, Research Professor, Srinivas University, India and Research Director, Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Urlabari – 3, Morang, Nepal.

*Corresponding Author Email: mishraanjay278@gmail.com

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Abstract: Casting delay is a significant contributor to the falling trend of concrete's compressive strength. Although it is preferable to lay fresh concrete as soon as the mixing procedure is done, this is not always possible due to many reasons. Improper handling methods, site organization, work scheduling and equipment breakdown, distance from central batching plant for ready-mix concrete as well as traffic conditions on the road are some reasons for the unanticipated elongated postponement. The main objective of this research was to analyze the impact of time elapsed between mixing and placing on compressive strength of concrete. Lab based experimental methods were used for this purpose.

The cement with standard consistency of 31%, initial setting time of 120 minutes, soundness of 6 mm was mixed with graded aggregates having LAA of 28.65%, AIV of 28.6 %, specific gravity of 2.59 (for coarse) and 2.65 (for fines) water having pH of 7.9. Concrete cubes were casted at different time delays and were tested at 7, 14 and 28 days for compressive strength.

Keywords: Concrete, Casting Delay, Setting Time, Compressive Strength of Concrete, M20

Introduction

Concrete is expected to be placed immediately after the cement, aggregates, and water has been mixed [1]. However, unexpected delays before placement can occur for a variety of reasons. This has an impact on the hardened concrete's compressive strength.

Quality assurance of intended quality is a concern for all project stakeholders, and any deficiencies in the quality control assurance components would have a negative influence on the project. If the quality of the concrete work is not correctly accomplished during the building phase, the hardened concrete is prone to acquire flaws such as cracking, honeycombing, volume changes, and loss of compressive strength (Mishra and Jha, 2019).

According to the cement setting and hardening principle, OPC has an initial setting time of 30 minutes and final setting time of 600 minutes. In Nepal, it has been discovered that the morning mix is used at a different frequency (time intervals) for concreting, which affects the strength of the concrete and increases the vulnerability of the structure as a

whole. IS 456-2000[3] recommends that the concrete be placed and compacted before the initial setting of the concrete begins, and that it not be delayed afterwards (Aryal and Mishra, 2020) . Even in professionally built buildings with plinth areas bigger than 1000 sq.ft, considerable attention is placed on design and details, while workmanship and supervision in such structures is typically less addressed. Most of the work is done by the labors themselves, without the assistance of construction or quality experts, which may be owing to a scarcity of competent specialists. Despite the fact that the structures are technically planned, inadequate understanding of concrete mixing and placement procedures and its workability will have a considerable influence on the compressive strength of the structural components and the life of the structure as a whole.

Although it is preferred to pour new concrete as quickly as the mixing procedure is done, concrete placement in its final position is frequently delayed due to variety of reasons. Improper concrete handling methods, site organization, work scheduling, and equipment breakdown are some of the causes of the unexpectedly long delay. The delay time for ready-mixed concrete is influenced by the distance of the sites from the central batching plant as well as the traffic conditions on the route. This is a particularly serious issue in hot weather. Indian Standard codes is being followed in Nepal but the results of past foreign researches on delayed casting-based research topics are contradictory with this IS codal provision [5,6,7,8]. Casting Delay of the concrete mix has certain effect on the compressive strength of the concrete but no test has been found done on this regard in Nepalese construction.

Statement of Problem

Understanding the impact of delayed casting on the compressive strength of concrete is crucial for ensuring the quality and durability of concrete structures (Sapkota, L. P., & Mishra, A. K. ,2021: Dhungana, A., Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S. ,2022). The study for obtaining valuable insights for concrete production and placement practices, ultimately contributing to the development of guidelines for optimizing the compressive strength of concrete under varying time elapsed conditions is a most(Mishra, A.K., Sudarsan, J.S., & Nithiyantham, S. ,2023: Adhikari, N., Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., 2022).

The main objective of this study is to assess how the time lag between concrete mixing and casting affects the compressive strength of the concrete. Specifically, the research will focus on determining the rate of change in compressive strength as the delay between mixing and placing increases.

Research Objectives

General Objective

The overall objective of this research is to analyze the impact of time elapsed between mixing and placing on compressive strength of concrete.

Specific Objectives

- To identify the optimum time between mixing and placing of concrete to achieve target strength.

- To study the effect of casting delay on the compressive strength of M20 grade concrete.

Time Delay in Placing Of Concrete

It is difficult to cast the whole structure monolithically if the concrete elements are large size; there are some limitations to the availability of formwork, concrete workers or supply of the fresh concrete. In such cases, it becomes necessary to perform structure elements in two or more stages, which leads to formation joints Cold joint is one of concreting problem due to delay of casting the second layer. Therefore, it is necessary to study the effect of delay in time period when casting the second layer. The results were investigated and it indicates that, in case of delaying in the time period for casting the second layer, there is a great effect on the mechanical properties of concrete (Pawar&Jadav, 2019; Muhammad et al, 2020) .

One of the most typical issues in the concrete business is concrete casting delay. Delays in the placement of concrete can be caused by a variety of issues, including malfunctioning casting technology, poor site conditions, and inexperienced handling, all of which result in material and money waste. The concrete that has been held for a long time before being cast has lost its workability and strength, and it may no longer be suitable for the purpose for which it was mixed .The addition of simply water to improve the workability of a time-lapsed concrete results in lower strength values, but experiments with the addition of cement, super plasticizers, retarders, fly ash, and other materials have provided sufficient measures and literature regarding increases in slump, compressive strength, and flexural strength [15].

One of the studies was focused on identifying the degree of craned concrete installation delays in Nigeria and their impact on concreting production. Multiple regression was used to analyze the productivity data and come up with a model that relates productivity to fractional delay. The results revealed an average delay of more than 23% of the pour time, with productivity dropping by more than 2.5 m³/h for every 10% increase in delay (Olatunde, Okunola, &Adesanya, 2011) .

According to Muchinyi and Smith, R.B.L. (Department of Civil Engineering, University of Nairobi), delays in delivery of ready mixed concrete which results in rejection can cause construction issues. Their research looked at the effects of casting delays and concrete disruption up to 480 minutes after blending. It was discovered that, if enough compaction is ensured, Delays in casting result in strength gain, and here the most significant element is workability [17, 18]. Furthermore, providing disruption to partially set concrete by putting fresh concrete in contact of it has no significant influence on the strength of the resultant structure (Sustainable Construction and Building Materials, 2019)

With incremental superplasticizer addition, casting delay generates an improvement in compressive strength in case of plain concrete. A delay of 120 minutes resulted in a 25% increase for plain concrete, and a 13–17% increase for superplasticizer concrete with incremental addition after 1.5 hours of delay (Ravindrarajah, 1985) .

For both OPC and PLC concrete samples, casting delay is a key variable in the falling trend of concrete compressive strength. After the first hour of mixing in the “no-water addition” case, the workability and compressive strength of concrete samples (both OPC and PLC) began to decline significantly. The compressive strength of concrete samples (both OPC and PLC) began to decline significantly after the final setting period in the "water addition" situation. (FST) ((Mahuz, Bhuiyan, &Oshin, 2020) .

In the reported weather conditions of 32°C (90°F) and 20% relative humidity, at which concrete mixes were made, it was found that prolonging mixing time and delaying the casting up to 40 min had beneficial effects on the strength of concrete (a increment of about 23% was obtained) ((Kayyali, 1984) .

Research Philosophy

Attached picture depicts the different stages in designing a research methodology by using the research onion framework as in figure 1.

Figure1: Research Onion

The single reality is taken from ontology part and measurable are taken from epistemology part. The overall research philosophy is Positivism is in which only "factual" information obtained from observation (the senses), including measurement, is reliable. The researcher's function in this positivist studies is confined to data gathering and objective interpretation. The study outcomes in these sorts of investigations are frequently apparent and quantitative.

Abduction approach for logical reasoning was followed in which the elements of both the inductive and deductive approaches were combined. Regarding methodological choice, both qualitative as well as quantitative methods were followed. So, it’s a mixed method. The research strategy was experimental. As the data were collected through the different laboratory tests, this study was experimental lab-based as well as field based

where delay pattern in placing concrete was observed in the field. The experiment was done on longitudinal time horizon. The study of a phenomena or a population over time is referred to as longitudinal research. The data collection methods were observation method and lab-based methods using several references such as (Mishra and Chaudhary,2018; Mishra et al, 2020; Mishra et al,2021, Banstola et al, 2021) .

Sampling

The compressive strength determined in the lab was used as the primary data for the study using several references such as (Mishra and Chaudhary,2018; Mishra et al, 2020; Mishra et al,2021, Banstola et al, 2021) . Because the initial setting time for OPC was assumed to be minimum of 30 minutes, three samples of M20 grade cubes, each casted at 30 minutes after mixing, 90 minutes, and 120 minutes of mixing, were tested for compressive strength after 7,14 and 28 days of curing. The total number of primary samples for this was 36 numbers. The samples were tested in the laboratories of the District Coordination Committee of Jhapa and the Infrastructure Development Office of Jhapa.

Research Matrix

The summary of the research process has been outlined as a research matrix in Table 1.

Table1: Research Matrix

SN	Research Objective	Data required	Collection tools	Analysis	Outcomes
1	To identify the optimum time between mixing and placing of concrete to achieve target strength.	Consistency Setting time Soundness Gradation pH Specific gravity and water absorption Abrasion resistance Impact resistance Compressive strength	Fine and coarse aggregates were collected from Biring crusher. Cement was obtained from nearest hardware and laboratory work was done.	28 days maximum compressive strength with corresponding time delay in casting was compared.	Optimum time of delay for which the the target strength was given by test results.
2	To study the effect of casting delay on the compressi-ve strength of M20 grade concrete.	Compressive strength	Cubes were prepared by mixing cement, aggregates, and water in the lab	Final compressive strengths of cubes made for different casting delays were analyzed and ANOVA test was carried out to see how significantly the casting delays within initial setting time affects the final compressive strength	The variation in compressive strength for cubes made for different casting delays within initial setting time was given by test results and tested weather the difference was significant or not.

Hypothesis Testing:

Analysis of Variance; The analysis of variance as F- statistical technique was used to test whether the difference between the means of three or more populations is significant or not [26].

Null hypothesis H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4$ (i.e. There is no significant difference in the means of compressive strength of different time delays within initial setting time.

Alternative hypothesis H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3 \neq \mu_4$ (i.e. There is significant difference in the means of compressive strength of different time delays within initial setting time.

Results and Discussion

Assessment of Optimum Time of Mixing Concrete

The study's major goal was to determine the optimum time for mixing concrete for target strength of concrete. Before initiating compressive strength test, tests for suitability of ingredient materials of concrete were performed. Concrete was casted with delay periods and no additional water was used for this. After 7 days, 14 days, and 28 days, the compressive strength test was performed. The findings were analyzed and discussed with existing literatures.

Consistency Test:

Table 2: Consistency Test Results

S.No	Cement weight in gram	% by water of dry cement	Amount of water added in ml	Penetration in mm
1	300	26	78	23
2	300	30	90	18
3	300	31	93	6

The standard consistency for cement under test was found out to be 31% of the dry weight of the cement. So, for the test minimum w/c of 0.31 is necessary to start the chemical reaction between water and cement, which results in the formation of a paste.

Setting Time:

- I. Normal consistency (P)= 31%
- II. Weight of cement (g) = 400
- III. Weight of water(g) = $0.85 * P = 26.35\% * 400 = 105.4$

Table 3: Setting time test results

S.No.	Setting Time (minutes)	Requirement as per (IS 8112, 1989)[27]	Requirement as per NS 49:253[5]	Results Obtained(minutes)
1	Initial Setting Time	30 (min)	45(min)	120
2	Final Setting Time	600(max)	600(max)	425

The initial setting time and final setting times were found to be 120 and 425 minutes respectively. These setting times are within the standards as prescribed in IS 8112-1989 and NS 49:253 for OPC cement. So, the cement used was found to be acceptable for the work.

Soundness Test:

Table 4: Soundness Test Results

Description	Requirement as per NS 49:253	Requirement as per IS 8112-1989	Result obtained (mm)
Soundness Test	10(max)	10(max)	6

The soundness test of cement was done with the help of Le-Chatelier and found out to be 6mm which is within the limits prescribed by NS 49:253 and IS 8112-1989. The capacity of hardened cement pastes to hold its volume after setting without delayed harmful expansion induced by free lime and magnesia is referred to as soundness. Hence, the cement used for test was said to be sound.

Sieve Analysis

The sieve analysis was carried out for both coarse as well as fine aggregates.

a. Coarse Aggregate:

The sieve analysis was carried out and checked for specification limit requirement for coarse aggregates is given in appendix 1.

Table 5: Sieve analysis result for coarse aggregate

Type of Material	20mm Aggregate (Crasher Plant)					
Total Wt., gm	53191					
I. S. Sieve (mm)	Specified requirement		Weight	Cum. Wt.	%	Remarks
	Min.	Max.	Retained gm	Passed gm	Passing	
40.00	100	100	0	53191	100.0	
20.00	95	100	1620	51571	97.0	
10.00	25	55	33211	18360	34.5	
4.75	0	10	17120	1240	2.3	
Pan			1240			

Figure 2: Percentage passing by weight vs sieve size for coarse aggregate

The result obtained was plotted to obtain sieve analysis curve as presented below. The curve is bound within the upper and lower limits as suggested by IS Code for 20 mm

b. Fine Aggregate:

Table 6: Sieve analysis result of fine aggregate

Type of Material:	Sand					
Weight of Sample:	4182.00					
Sieve Size mm	Retained	Cum. Wt.	Cum. %	% Passing	Specified requirement (Passing)	
	Weight	Retained	Retained		Min.	Max.
10.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100	100
4.75	201.00	201.00	4.81	95.19	90	100
2.36	415.00	616.00	14.73	85.27	60	95
1.18	885.00	1501.00	35.89	64.11	30	70
0.60	1610.00	3111.00	74.39	25.61	15	34
0.30	570.00	3681.00	88.02	11.98	5	30
0.15	415.00	4096.00	97.94	2.06	0	10
Pan	86.00					
Total Wt.	4182.00					

The result obtained was plotted to obtain sieve analysis curve as presented below

Figure 3: Percentage passing by weight vs sieve size for fine aggregate

The curve is bound within the upper and lower limits as suggested by IS Code for zone I.

pH Test

Table 7: pH test result

S.No.	Parameter	Observed Value	NDWQS
1	pH at 26.2 degree celsius	7.9	6.5-8.5

As per the result, pH of water was found to be 7.9 which is within the limits prescribed by Nepal Drinking Water Quality Standards (NDWQS). Hence the water can be used for the purpose of mixing and curing.

Specific Gravity Test

Table 8: Specific Gravity for Coarse Aggregate

S.No.	Description	Sample1(gm)	Sample2(gm)	Sample3(gm)	Remarks
1	Mass of Empty Pycnometer in gm (M1)	660	660	660	
2	Mass of Pycnometer + dry aggregate in gm (M2)	932	1090	1020	
3	Mass of Pycnometer + dry aggregate + water in gm (M3)	1290	1411	1350	
4	Mass of Pycnometer + water in gm (M4)	1127	1140	1130	
5	Specific gravity of aggregate (G) = $(M2 - M1) / [(M4 - M1) - (M3 - M2)]$	2.50	2.70	2.57	
Average Specific gravity		2.59			

As per test results for coarse aggregate, the average specific gravity is found to be $2.59 > 2.5$, which was acceptable.

Table 9: Specific Gravity for Fine Aggregate

S.No.	Description	Sample1 (gm)	Sample2 (gm)	Sample3 (gm)	Remarks
1	Mass of Empty Pycnometer in gm (M1)	660	660	660	
2	Mass of Pycnometer + dry aggregate in gm (M2)	938	1090	1021	
3	Mass of Pycnometer + dry aggregate + water in gm (M3)	1298	1410	1355	
4	Mass of Pycnometer + water in gm (M4)	1127	1138	1131	
5	Specific gravity of aggregate (G) = $(M2 - M1) / [(M4 - M1) - (M3 - M2)]$	2.60	2.72	2.64	
Average Specific gravity		2.65			

As per test results for fine aggregate, the average specific gravity for fine aggregate was found to be $2.65 > 2.5$, which was acceptable.

Loss Angles Abrasion (LAA) Test

Table 10: Loss Angles abrasion test result

Grading	Units	Sample 1	Sample2	Specified
Number of Revolutions		500		
Total Weight of Test Sample	(gm)	5000	5000	
Weight of Test Sample Retained on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)	3575	3559	
Weight of Test Sample passed on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)	1425	1441	
Percent Loss	%	28.5	28.8	Max \leq 30%
Average Loss Abrasion Percent Value	%	28.65		

Average Loss Abrasion Percent Value was found to be 28.65% which was acceptable as it was within maximum specified value of 30%.

Aggregate Impact Value (AIV) Test

Table 11: Aggregate Impact Value Test result

S.No.	Description	Units	Test number 1	Test number 2	Remarks
A1	Weight of cylindrical measure + sample, A1	gm	958.0	962.0	
A2	Weight of Cylindrical Measure A2	gm	591.5	591.5	
A	Weight of Sample =(A1-A2)	gm	366.5	370.5	
B	Aggregate weight retained on 2.36mm sieve after the test	gm	262.0	264.0	
C	Aggregate weight passing on 2.36 mm sieve after the test	gm	104.5	106.5	
D	Total weight =B+C	gm	366.5	370.5	
E	Aggregate Impact Value = percent fines = (C/A) *100	%	28.5	28.7	
F	Average Aggregate Impact Value	%	28.6		
G	specifications	%	≤ 30		

Average AIV was found to be 28.6% which was acceptable as it was within maximum specified value of 30%.

Compressive Strength Tests

The compressive strength tests were carried out at 7,14 and 28 days of casting concrete for different time delays.

7Days Test Results:

Table 12: Results of Compressive Strength after 7 Days of Casting

Time (Minutes)	Load (KN)	Compressive Strength (Mpa)	Avg. Strength	Deviation from avg. strength (%)	Remarks
30	435	19.33	19.04	1.52	Individual compressive strength is Within ±15% variation of the mean compressive strength.
30	430	19.11		0.37	
30	420	18.67		-1.94	
60	475	21.11	19.78	6.72	
60	390	17.33		-12.39	
60	470	20.89		5.61	
90	490	21.78	21.63	0.69	
90	465	20.67		-4.44	
90	505	22.44		3.74	
120	375	16.67	15.48	7.69	
120	305	13.56		-12.4	
120	365	16.22		4.78	

The average 7 days compressive strength of concrete casted after 30 ,60, 90 and 120 minutes of adding water showed that the strength was increasing from 30 minutes to 90 minutes and decreasing afterwards. The maximum individual compressive strength of 22.44 Mpa was obtained at 90 minutes. Most of the individual strength nearly meet 65% of the target strength. Hence, the test showed good result at 7 days.

14 Days Test Result

Table 13: Results of Compressive Strength after 14 Days of Casting

Time (Minutes)	Load (KN)	Compressive Strength (Mpa)	Avg. Strength	Deviation from avg. strength (%)	Remarks
30	505	22.44		-5.04	Individual compressive strength is Within $\pm 15\%$ variation of the mean compressive strength.
30	560	24.89	23.63	5.33	
30	530	23.56		-0.3	
60	570	25.33		-0.59	
60	600	26.67	25.48	4.67	
60	550	24.44		-4.08	
90	610	27.11		1.96	
90	585	26	26.59	-2.22	
90	600	26.67		0.3	
120	520	23.11		1.32	
120	505	22.44	22.81	-1.62	
120	515	22.89		0.35	

The average 14 days compressive strength of concrete casted after 30 ,60, 90 and 120 minutes of adding water showed that the strength was increasing from 30 minutes to 90 minutes and decreasing afterwards. It was following the analogous trend with that of 7 days compressive strength. The maximum individual compressive strength of 27.11 Mpa was obtained at 90 minutes. Most of the individual strength nearly meet the target strength. Hence, the test showed good result at 14 days.

28 days Test Result:

Table 14: Results of Compressive Strength after 28 Days of Casting

Time (Minutes)	Load (KN)	Compressive Strength (Mpa)	Avg. Strength	Deviation from avg. strength (%)	Remarks
30	585	26		-4.62	Individual compressive strength is Within $\pm 15\%$ variation of the mean compressive strength.
30	655	29.11	27.26	6.79	
30	600	26.67		-2.16	
60	650	28.89		0	
60	690	30.67	28.89	6.16	
60	610	27.11		-6.16	
90	630	28		-4.31	
90	695	30.89	29.26	5.57	
90	650	28.89		-1.26	
120	605	26.89		-0.81	
120	625	27.78	27.11	2.47	
120	600	26.67		-1.62	

The average 28 days compressive strength of concrete casted after 30 ,60, 90 and 120 minutes of adding water showed that the strength is increasing from 30 minutes to 90 minutes and decreasing afterwards. It was following the similar trend with that of 7- and 14-days compressive strength respectively. The maximum individual compressive strength of 30.89 Mpa was obtained at 90 minutes.

Comparison of 7 days, 14 days and 28 days test results:

Table 15 shows comparison for mean compressive strengths at 7, 14 and 28 days of casting for different casting delays.

Table 15: Comparative Charts for Mean Compressive Strength Results at 7, 14 and 28 Days of Casting

Time elapsed in placing (minute)	Mean 7 Days	Mean 14 days	Mean 28 days
30	19.04	23.63	27.26
60	19.78	25.48	28.89
90	21.63	26.59	29.26
120	15.48	22.81	27.11

Check for acceptance

From IS: 456:2000

Table 16: Characteristic Compressive Strength Compliance Requirement

Grade	Mean of the Group	Individual test results in Mpa
For M20 or above	$\geq f_{ck} + 0.825 * \text{standard deviation}$ or $(f_{ck} + 4)$ whichever is greater	$\geq f_{ck} - 4$
	Hence, group mean should be minimum 24 Mpa	

(Source: Table 11 and Table 4 of IS 456:2000) [1]

From the test results of 28 days compressive strength of concrete cubes, it can be seen that the individual cube strengths were greater than 24 Mpa as per IS code and the group mean strength of each time set was also greater than the minimum required as suggested by IS code 456:2000. Hence, the concrete sample was found to be acceptable.

Also, from the tables it can be seen that the individual 28 days compressive strength of cube at each time set was within $\pm 15\%$ variation of the group means which was within the limits as suggested by IS code 456:2000. Hence, the concrete and the test results were found to be acceptable.

Effect of Casting Delay on Compressive Strength

The result of compressive strength at 7 days, 14 days and 28 days were illustrated by the figure 4, figure 5 and figure 6.

Figure 4: Variation of compressive strength at 7 days of casting

Figure 5: Variation of compressive strength at 14 days of casting

Figure 6: Variation of compressive strength at 28 days of casting

Figure 7: Comparative charts for Mean Compressive Strength at 7, 14 & 28 Days

Discussion

From laboratory quality test results for cement and aggregates, it can be seen that the materials for concreting were within required standard. The compressive strength of concrete cubes at each time of casting was found to be increasing from 30 minutes to 90 minutes of adding water. Compressive strength of concrete was found to be at peak around 90 minutes which was within the initial setting time of the corresponding cement (Maruti Cement) i.e., 120 minutes. But each time, target strength was well achieved for

each individual tests. So, it can be said that the optimum time for casting concrete is within initial setting time to achieve the target strength. This finding fulfilled the 1st objective of this research.

This result could be compared with previous literatures. A weight-based mix ratio of 1:1.5:1.5 had been used in the previous study by (Mahuz, Bhuiyan, & Oshin, 2020) for OPC with normal consistency 25%, IST= 96 min and FST = 290 min. The slump of 75 mm was recorded for the mix. Though different mix volume with normal consistency 31%, and mix ratio 1:1.38:2.2 was used in our research, it was seen that in previous study there was huge difference in compressive strength after 60 minutes of casting. This might be due to difference in IST and FST. Also targeted workability of 75 mm was difficult to be achieved after 120 minutes during the test with w/c of 0.40 in our study, so the time elapsed was limited to only 120 minutes i.e., within the initial setting time. The compressive strength of concrete was drastically reduced after first 60 minutes of casting in previous study which was even substantially below the target strength but our result contradicted to the theory as the target strength was well achieved for delay within initial setting time.

All of the individual strength exceeded the target strength of concrete at 28 days which was 24 Mpa. Analysis of variance was carried to test significance of the difference of mean compressive strengths for different time delays out in accordance with the process outlined in methodology.

The problem is

Table 17: Time Delay in Placing

Compressive Strength (MPA)	Time Delay in Placing			
	30 minutes	60 minutes	90 minutes	120 minutes
Test 1	26	28.89	28	26.89
Test 2	29.11	30.67	30.89	27.78
Test 3	26.67	27.11	28.89	26.67

Null hypothesis H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4$ (i.e. There is no significant difference in the means of compressive strength of different time delays within initial setting time.

Alternative hypothesis H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3 \neq \mu_4$ (i.e. There is significant difference in the means of compressive strength of different time delays within initial setting time.

Based on Appendix -C, Critical value: Tabulated value of F at 5% level of significance for 3 and 9 d.f. is 3.86

Decision: Since the calculated value is less than critical value of F, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the means of compressive strength of different time delays within initial setting time.

From this analysis, it can be said that if concrete is casted within initial setting time, the final strength does not vary significantly [26, 27, 28, 29&30].

This result could be compared with previous literatures. From the result of ANOVA test in this research, it was found that there is no significant difference in the means of compressive strength of different time delays within initial setting time. As per (Mahuz, Bhuiyan, & Oshin, 2020), the compressive strength of concrete was drastically reduced after first 60 minutes of casting even substantially below the target strength but our result

contradicted to the theory as results were similar. The no significant difference has also been derived from analysis of variance in our study.

As per the study by (Ravindrarajah, 1985), it was concluded that a delay of 120 minutes caused the 28-day compressive strength to increase from 30.5 to 38.0 N/mm² for plain concrete and 35.0 to 37.2 N/mm² for super plasticized concrete. But such significant increment was not observed for plain concrete in our study as the results were similar during 120 minutes.

In the reported weather conditions of 32°C (90°F) and 20% R.H. at which concrete mixes were made, it was found that prolonging mixing time and delaying the casting up to 40 min had beneficial effects on the strength of concrete (a increment of about 23% was obtained) as per findings of study by (Kayyali, 1984). But such significant increment was not found in our study.

Here the results of above-mentioned previous researches were contradictory with each other as well as contradictory with the codal provision too. But results of this research is contradictory with above mentioned previous two researches but agrees with codal provision as mentioned in clause 13.2 of (IS 456, 2000) where it has been instructed that concrete shall be placed and compacted before initial setting of concrete completes.

Conclusions

Since every cement has its unique setting time, the knowledge of setting time of cement is a must during casting process. In case of mass concreting in the field, there may be delay in casting due to many reasons but casting should not be delayed beyond initial setting time. So it can be concluded that optimum time for placing concrete is within the initial setting time.

From the test it can be seen that the final strength of concrete is increasing due to delay casting upto 90 minutes and decreasing thereafter but the target strength for each time of casting is reached and individual strengths also do not vary significantly for different casting delays within initial setting time as depicted by the test for analysis of variance. So it has been concluded that if the casting is done within initial setting time no significant effect is seen on the compressive strength of concrete.

Author Contributions

The first author conducted the experiment under instruction of second author. The second author wrote the paper and completes the research on the basis of first author experiment and collected data and research work as per regulatory guidelines of Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal.

Conflict of Interest

The research team will take overall responsibility of guaranteeing that the dignity, rights to know, decisions of taking part in interview, safety & Security, privacy, confidentiality, right to know the result & wellbeing of the research participants under the guideline of MBMAN Research Policy,2019.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX-A

Appendix A: Gradation requirement for coarse aggregates

Group	Grade Designation	Specified Characteristic Compressive Strength of 150 mm cube at 28 days in N/mm ²
(1)	(2)	(3)
Ordinary Concrete	M 10	10
	M 15	15
	M 20	20
Standard Concrete	M 25	25
	M 30	30
	M 35	35
	M 40	40
	M 45	45
	M 50	50
High Strength Concrete	M 55	55
	M 60	60
	M 65	65
	M 70	70
	M 75	75
	M 80	80

(Source Table 2 IS 383:1970, Specification for coarse and fine aggregates from natural sources for concrete, second revision)

Appendix -B

Graduation requirement for coarse aggregates

IS Seive Designation	Percentage Passing For			
	Grading Zone I	Grading Zone II	Grading Zone III	Grading Zone IV
10 mm	100	100	100	100
4.75 mm	90-100	90-100	90-100	95-100
2.36mm	60-95	75-100	85-100	95-100
1.18 mm	30-70	55-90	75-100	90-100
600 micron	15-34	35-59	60-79	80-100
300 micron	5-20	8-30	12-40	15-50
150 micron	0-10	0-10	0-10	0-15

Source: Table 5 IS 383:1970, Specification for coarse and fine aggregates from natural sources for concrete, second revision)

Appendix-C

ANOVA test

X_A	X_B	X_C	X_D	X_A^2	X_B^2	X_C^2	X_D^2
26	28.89	28	26.89	676.00	834.63	784.00	723.07
29.11	30.67	30.89	27.78	847.39	940.65	954.19	771.73
26.67	27.11	28.89	26.67	711.29	734.95	834.63	711.29
$\Sigma X_A =$	$\Sigma X_B =$	$\Sigma X_C =$	$\Sigma X_D =$	$\Sigma X_A^2 =$	$\Sigma X_B^2 =$	$\Sigma X_C^2 =$	$\Sigma X_D^2 =$
81.78	86.67	87.78	81.34	2234.68	2510.23	2572.82	2206.09
Grand Total (T) = $\Sigma X_A + \Sigma X_B + \Sigma X_C + \Sigma X_D =$				337.57			
Correction factor (C.F.) = $T^2/n =$				9496.13			
Total Sum of square (TSS) = $\Sigma X_A^2 + \Sigma X_B^2 + \Sigma X_C^2 + \Sigma X_D^2 - C.F. =$				27.70			
Sum of square between samples (SSC) = $(\Sigma X_A)^2/n_A + (\Sigma X_B)^2/n_B + (\Sigma X_C)^2/n_C + (\Sigma X_D)^2/n_D - C.F. =$				10.935			
Sum of square within samples (SSW) = $TSS - SSC =$				16.77			
Source of Variation	Sum of squares	d.f.	Mean sum of squares	F-ratio			
Between samples	10.935	3	3.64501	1.7391068			
Within samples	16.77	8	2.09591				

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